

COMPARATIVE STUDY OF ANTI-NUTRITIONAL CONTENTS OF *Enterolobium cyclocarpum* SEEDS BASED TOTAL MIXED RATIONS AND FEED BLOCKS

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ABSTRACT

The study was carried out to evaluate comparative study of anti-nutritional contents of *Enterolobium cyclocarpum* seeds based total mixed rations (TMR) and feed blocks (FB). The materials that were used for the complete feed blocks production are *E. cyclocarpum* seeds, cassava peels, wood ash, common salt, groundnut haulms and cassava starch. The *E. cyclocarpum* seeds were toasted for about 15 minutes at 170°C until the testa started breaking. Feed blocks (FB) and Total Mixed Ration (TMR) containing varying levels of Toasted *Enterolobium cyclocarpum* Seeds Meal: TECSM (0g/kg, 60g/kg, 120g/kg, 180g/kg, and 240g/kg) were formulated. The TECSM inclusion levels for FB1, FB2, FB3, and FB5 were 0g/kg, 60g/kg, 120g/kg, 180g/kg, and 240g/kg, respectively. TMR1, TMR2, TMR3, TMR4, and TMR5 were evaluated at TECSM inclusion levels of 0g/kg, 60g/kg, 120g/kg, 180g/kg, and 240g/kg respectively. Samples of raw *E. cyclocarpum* seeds, toasted *E. cyclocarpum* seeds, and feed blocks were oven dried at 65°C until a constant weight was attained and ground for the determination of Tannin, Saponin and Oxalate. Data obtained were subjected to one-way analysis of variance and Significant means were separated using Duncan's multiple range tests. There were significant differences ($p < 0.05$) in the anti-nutritional content of the test samples. The saponin content ranges from 0.06 % in FB 3 to 0.80 % in TMR 3 and TMR 1. The tannin contents were significantly different ($p < 0.05$) across all treatments. The tannin content value ranges from 0.08 raw *E. cyclocarpum* seeds to 0.19 in FB 2 and FB 3 while the oxalate content was significantly the highest in raw *Enterolobium cyclocarpum* seeds (8.80mg/kg) and lowest in FB 2, FB 5, TMR 4 and TMR 5 (2.20) mg/kg. Toasting *Enterolobium cyclocarpum* seeds reduced the saponin and oxalate contents as against the raw *E. cyclocarpum* seeds.

Keywords: Tannin, *Enterolobium cyclocarpum*, Feedblocks and Total Mixed Rations.

INTRODUCTION

Ruminants' primary feed sources are natural pastures composed of grasses, legumes. These are dependent on rainfall, which varies greatly in the northern region of Nigeria, where the majority of these animals are raised. As a result of the low yield and availability of poor quality herbage, there is a lack of energy and protein feedstuffs during the dry season, which is a major setback to ruminant livestock production in the tropics (Aruwayo & Maigandi, 2013). Recent investigations have showed that several indigenous multipurpose tree species, particularly *E. cyclocarpum*, are evergreen and yield seeds with a high protein content. (Arigbede *et al.*, 2008), he also discovered that these seeds are edible and contain a considerable amount of nutrients to support animal productivity. Although the seeds are high in protein, they are limited by a large concentration of anti-nutritional chemicals formed by plant secondary metabolism. This necessitated the compelling reason to carry out a research on the comparative study of anti-nutritional contents of *Enterolobium cyclocarpum* seeds in order to improve the feeding value of this important feed resource.

Materials and Methods

Experimental sites

The *Enterolobium cyclocarpum* seeds based complete feed blocks and *Brachiaria ruziziensis* hay production were carried out at the Pasture and Range experimental unit of the Directorate of University Farms (DUFARMS) while the anti-nutritional factors determination of the experimental feed blocks was carried out at the laboratory of the Department of Pasture and Range Management.

Experimental Materials

The materials that were used for the complete feed blocks production are *E. cyclocarpum* seeds, cassava peels, wood ash, common salt, groundnut haulms and cassava starch. The *E. cyclocarpum* seeds were toasted for about 15 minutes at 170°C until the testa started breaking.

Experimental Procedures

Feed blocks (FB) and Total Mixed Ration (TMR) containing varying levels of Toasted *Enterolobium cyclocarpum* Seeds Meal: TECSM (0g/kg, 60g/kg, 120g/kg, 180g/kg, and 240g/kg) were formulated. The TECSM inclusion levels for FB1, FB2, FB3, and FB5 were 0g/kg, 60g/kg, 120g/kg, 180g/kg, and 240g/kg, respectively. TMR1, TMR2, TMR3, TMR4, and TMR5 were evaluated at TECSM inclusion levels of 0g/kg, 60g/kg, 120g/kg, 180g/kg, and 240g/kg respectively. Samples of raw *E. cyclocarpum* seeds (RAECSM), toasted *E. cyclocarpum* seeds (TECSM), and feed blocks were oven dried at 65°C until a constant weight was attained and ground for the determination of Tannin, Saponin and Oxalate.

Statistical analysis

The statistical evaluation was done by the analysis of variance (ANOVA) and significant means were separated by Duncan multiple range test at 0.05 probability level using SAS® 9.0 version and results were visualized using Microsoft Excel.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

The anti-nutritional contents (Saponin, Oxalate and Tannin) of raw *Enterolobium cyclocarpum* seeds, toasted *Enterolobium cyclocarpum* seeds meal, total mixed rations and feed blocks containing graded level of toasted. There were significant differences ($p < 0.05$) in the Saponin content of the test samples with the saponin content ranging from 0.06 % in FB 3 to 0.80 % The TMR 1 and TMR 3 had the highest Saponin (0.8 %) content and FB 3 had the least saponin content (Figure 1)

The tannin contents were significantly different ($p < 0.05$) across all treatments. The tannin content value ranges from 0.08 % raw *Enterolobium cyclocarpum* seeds to 0.19 % in FB 2 and FB 3 (Figure 2) while in Figure 3, the oxalate content was significantly the highest in raw *Enterolobium cyclocarpum* seeds (8.80 mg/Kg) and lowest in FB 2, FB 5, TMR 4 and TMR 5 (2.20 mg/kg).

Figure 1: Saponin contents of raw seeds, toasted seeds, total mixed rations and feed blocks containing graded level of toasted *Enterolobium cyclocarpum* seeds meal

RAECSM = A, TECSM = B, FB1 = C, FB2 = D, FB3 = E, FB4 = F, FB5 = G, TMR1 = H, TMR2 = I, TMR3 = J, TMR4 = K, TMR5 = L

Figure 2: Tannin contents of raw seeds, toasted seeds, total mixed rations and feed blocks containing graded level of toasted *Enterolobium cyclocarpum* seeds meal

RAECSM = A, TECSM = B, FB1 = C, FB2 = D, FB3 = E, FB4 = F, FB5 = G, TMR1 = H, TMR2 = I, TMR3 = J, TMR4 = K, TMR5 = L

Figure 3: Oxalate contents of raw seeds, toasted seeds, total mixed rations and feed blocks containing graded level of toasted *Enterolobium cyclocarpum* seeds meal

RAECSM = A, TECSM = B, FB1 = C, FB2 = D, FB3 = E, FB4 = F, FB5 = G, TMR1 = H, TMR2 = I, TMR3 = J, TMR4 = K, TMR5 = L

Discussion

The saponin content as recorded in this study ranges from 0.06 % in FB 3 to 0.80 % in TMR 3 and TMR 1. These values were similar to the values (0.00 to 3.92%) as reported by Edeoga *et al.*, (2005) when phytochemical constituents of some medicinal plants were evaluated and also similar to the values of 0.20 to 0.31% reported by (Isah *et al.*, 2011) when the effect of anti-nutritional factors on rumen bacteria of

WAD goats fed tropical browse species and crop by products were analysed. The saponin content of all the treatments in this study fell within the 3% safe range reported by (Anhwange *et al.*, 2009).

The tannin content value as recorded in this study ranges from 0.08 raw seeds to 0.19 in FB 2 and FB 3, however, these values are significantly lower than the values (6.08 to 15.25%) reported by (Edeoga *et al.*, 2005) when phytochemical constituents of some medicinal plants were evaluated and also similar to the values (0.02 to 0.08%) reported by (Isah *et al.*, 2011) when the effect of anti-nutritional factors on rumen bacteria of WAD goats fed tropical browse species and crop by products were analysed.

The oxalate contents value as recorded in this study ranges from (2.20 mg/Kg or 0.00022%) in FB 2, FB 5, TMR 4 and TMR 5 to (8.80mg/Kg or 0.00088%) in raw seeds, this is lower than the values of 0.43 to 0.68% reported by Isah *et al.*, (2011) when the effect of anti-nutritional factors on rumen bacteria of WAD goats fed tropical browse species and crop by products were analysed.

CONCLUSION

From the results of this study, it can be concluded that: The treatments in this study have shown low levels of anti-nutrients within tolerable levels. Toasting *Enterolobium cyllocarpum* seeds reduced the saponin and oxalate content as against the raw *Enterolobium cyllocarpum* seeds.

Based on the results of this study, Toasted *Enterolobium cyllocarpum* seeds meal up to 240g/kg can be included in feed blocks and total mixed rations. The inclusion of TECSM and ECFM in feed blocks for ruminant animals will greatly influence the utilization of nutrients in the animal and allow a synchronized supply of nutrients, resulting in their enhanced growth.

REFERENCES

- Amadi, B. A., Agomuo, E. N., and Ibegbulem, C. O. 2004. Research Methods in Biochemistry, Supreme Publishers, Owerri, Nigeria.
- Anhwange, B.A., Ugye, J.T. and Nyiatagher, T.D. 2009. Chemical composition of Musa sapientum peels. *Electronic Journal of Environmental, Agricultural. And Food Chemical*. 86: 437 – 444.
- Arigbede, O. M., Anele, U., Jolaosho, A. O., Olanite, J. A., Onifade, J. S., & Waheb, T. A. (2008). Chemical composition and *in vitro* gas production of African Bread fruit (*Treculia africana*) var. Decne. *Achivos de Zootecnia*, 58(28), 113-121.
- Aruwayo, A., Maigandi, S. A., Malami, B. S., Daneji, A. I., Saulawa, L. A. and Garba, M. G. (2013). Nutritional evaluation of alkali treated neem kernel cake fed to fattening rams. *Pakistan Journal of Nutrition*, 12(3): 224-228. Available online at <http://www.academicjournals.org/AJAR>.
- Edeoga, H. O., Okwu, D. E. and Mbaebie, B. O. (2005). Phytochemical constituents of some Nigerian Medicinal plants. *African Journal of Biotechnology*, 4: 685- 688.
- Isah, O. A., Fayemi, P. O., Gazaly, M. B. and Aderinboye, R. Y. (2011). Nutritional characteristics of four browse plants consumed by free-ranging ruminants in Western part of Nigeria. *African Journal of Agricultural Research*, 7(12): 1944- 1949.
- Munro, A. and Bassir, O.1969. Oxalate in Nigerian vegetables,” *W.A Journal of Biological and Applied Chemistry*, 12(1): 4-8
- Obadoni, B. O. and Ochuko, P. O. 2002. Phytochemical studies and comparative efficacy of the crude extracts of some haemostatic plants in Edo and Delta States of Nigeria, *Global Journal of Pure and Applied Sciences*, 8(2): 203–208